

EFFECTS OF ARTIFICIAL AGEING ON SEED GERMINATION INDEX OF SOYBEAN

S. N. Devkule*, R. C. Mahajan H.V. Kalpande,

Department of Agricultural Botany,

Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani 431402 Maharashtra, India.

sndevkule@gmail.com

(MS Received: 13.08.2023; MS Revised:06.10.2023; MS Accepted:07.10.2023)

MS 3115

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL BOTANY.)

Abstract

The present investigation was undertaken at the Experimental Farm, Department of Agricultural Botany, VNMKV, Parbhani, Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, VNMKV, Parbhani, Quality Control Laboratory, MSSC Ltd., Parbhani and Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, College of Agriculture, Golegaon, Hingoli with soybean varieties viz: MAUS-71, MAUS-158, JS-335 and MAUS-162. The studies on effects of ageing revealed that, the seeds of all varieties (MAUS-71, MAUS-158, JS-335 and MAUS-162) were aged artificially at various time (24, 48, 72, 96 and 120 Hs.) and temperature (41^oc, 42^oc, 43^oc, 44^oc and 45^oc) variables. Soybean variety MAUS-162 was found to be better in respect of moisture percentage, germination, germination index, seedling length, seed vigour index and electrical conductivity as compared to MAUS-71, MAUS-158 and JS-335 at the end of 120 hrs. and 240 days of storage period. The soybean variety MAUS-162 was found to be better in respect of biochemical parameters i.e., malondialdehyde, superoxide dismutase, peroxide activity, protein, oil and dehydrogenase activity.

Keywords: soybean, ageing, temperature

Introduction

Soybean [*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill] is an important oil crop in the family Leguminosae, subfamily Papilionaceae, and genus *Glycine* L. Soybean is of particular importance in times of energy crisis and closure and plays central role in agriculture, and export. It has now become an oil and seed crop and is the cheapest alternative source of high-quality protein and cooking oil. Soybeans are high in protein and a rich source of carbohydrates and fats. They are a good source of vitamins, minerals and beneficial plant compounds, such as isoflavones. Soybeans have great potential as a particularly nutritious and protein-rich food. In general, stronger seeds can withstand high temperatures and high humidity while producing normal seedlings. Field appearance and seed storage capacity are closely related to seed vigor, which in turn, is negatively affected by different aging periods and storage conditions. The quality of soybean seeds is easily degraded, making it difficult to preserve for a long time. The physiological properties and storage capacity of seeds are influenced by humidity, which in-turn is controlled by the relative humidity of the surrounding air. Seeds are hygroscopic, they tend to absorb or lose moisture causing various biochemical changes in soybeans.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation was carried out aiming at assessment of seed viability of plant species with high oil content and germination after seed had been stored and aged for certain period. Based on the aged seed vigour assessment, we can establish its field emergence capacity and possibility of forming vigorous and healthy plants which will be high yielding. The experimental material for the present investigation consists of four soybeans (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill.) varieties representing two maturity groups viz., MAUS-71 and MAUS-158 (Early maturity group: 93-95 days) and JS-335 and MAUS-162 (Late maturity group: 95-103 days). The seed material was evaluated for different seed quality parameters under natural and accelerated ageing conditions. Seed quality parameters were judged at 0, 60, 120, 180 and 240 days of storage.

Results and Discussion

The data on effect of varieties, temperature and storage hours on germination index of soybean seed during artificial ageing are presented in Table 1 and Fig. 1

The data revealed that the mean germination index percentage influenced significantly during all the storage periods. It was also noticed that seed germination index decreased with the advancement of storage period irrespective of varieties, temperature and storage hours. The significant differences in germination index of soybean varieties under study during all the storage periods (AA) were observed. The initial mean germination index of varieties MAUS-162, MAUS-158, MAUS-71 and JS-335 were 23.14, 22.45, 21.33 and 21.29 respectively. The soybean variety, MAUS-162 exhibited significantly higher (19.03) germination index than MAUS-158 (16.74), MAUS-71 (16.80) and JS-335 (12.18) at AA for 72 hrs. and 43^oC temperature of storage periods and at the transition point for soybean storage period.

Whereas, the lower germination index was observed when soybean genotype stored at 45^oC temperature for 120 hrs in JS-335 (2.43), MAUS-71 (3.12), MAUS-158 (3.83) and MAUS-162 (5.12) respectively. There was a linear decrease in germination index with an advancement of accelerated ageing period. It might have led to various biochemical changes in sub cellular system and membrane degradation which affected the germination index since seeds were exposed to highly adverse condition of temperature and storage hours. Similar results were reported in soybean (Dumbre, 2007), field bean (Narayanswamy and reddy, 1996), bitter melon (Shantappa *et al.*, 2006) and rice (Singh and Kanujia, 2006). Rahman *et al.*, (2010) found similar results who reported that highest germination index was obtained from 50 percent RH and lowest from 80 percent RH. The germination index was decreased with subsequent increase in storage period. This might be due to damage of proteins and nucleic acids, membrane enzyme etc.

Table 1 : Effect of artificial ageing on seed Germination Index of soybean varieties

V X T X H Mean Table

	V1=MAUS-71					V2=MAUS-158					V3=JS-335					V4=MAUS-162				
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
H1	21.33	20.89	18.42	18.49	16.83	22.45	20.42	18.43	17.05	16.67	21.29	20.34	19.70	15.89	16.05	23.14	22.08	20.54	19.13	19.95
H2	21.07	19.63	18.18	16.31	14.45	20.76	18.47	17.48	14.58	13.83	20.92	18.30	16.93	11.62	11.92	21.69	20.27	20.33	15.13	12.67
H3	20.38	17.57	16.80	14.51	11.04	19.18	17.05	16.74	13.92	10.07	19.50	14.10	12.18	10.17	8.14	21.48	20.53	19.03	13.20	12.48
H4	18.64	16.04	14.43	10.34	6.98	17.30	15.17	13.28	9.60	5.14	16.27	10.82	8.03	6.07	4.32	20.79	18.64	17.31	7.57	6.98
H5	16.54	11.28	10.58	8.31	3.12	15.27	12.83	10.47	6.78	3.83	12.70	6.77	5.43	4.18	2.43	18.72	15.38	14.37	5.27	5.12

Note V = Variety

V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162

T = Temperature

T1=41^oC, T2=42^oC, T3=43^oC, T4=44^oC, T5=45^oC

H = Hours

H1=24hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.

VxT

	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	Mean V
V1=MAUS-71	19.59	17.08	15.68	13.59	10.48	15.29
V2=MAUS-158	18.99	16.79	15.28	12.39	9.91	14.67
V3=JS-335	18.14	14.07	12.45	9.59	8.57	12.56
V4=MAUS-162	21.16	19.38	18.32	12.06	11.44	16.47
Mean T	19.47	16.83	15.43	11.91	10.10	

VxH

	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	Mean V
V1=MAUS-71	19.19	17.93	16.06	13.29	9.97	15.29
V2=MAUS-158	19.00	17.02	15.39	12.10	9.84	14.67
V3=JS-335	18.65	15.94	12.82	9.10	6.30	12.56

TxH

	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	Mean T
T1	22.05	21.11	20.14	18.25	15.81	19.47
T2	20.93	19.17	17.31	15.17	11.57	16.83
T3	19.27	18.23	16.19	13.26	10.21	15.43
T4	17.64	14.41	12.95	8.40	6.14	11.91
T5	17.38	13.22	10.43	5.86	3.63	10.10
Mean H	19.46	17.23	15.40	12.19	9.47	

Note V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162
 T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45°C
 H = Hours H1=24 hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.

TABLE OF SEM, SED AND C.D.

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(V)	0.14	0.07	0.05
Factor(T)	0.15	0.08	0.05
Interaction V X T	0.30	0.15	0.11
Factor(H)	0.15	0.08	0.05
Interaction V X H	0.30	0.15	0.11
Interaction T X H	0.34	0.17	0.12
Interaction V X T X H	0.68	0.34	0.24

Note V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162
 T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45°C
 H = Hours H1=24 hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hs.

Fig. 1: Effect of artificial ageing on seed Germination Index of soybean varieties

Note V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162

T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45°C

H = Hours H1=24hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.

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